

Communication channels survey

My name is *****. I am a ***** at *****.

I am inviting you to participate in a survey about the communication channels used by the development teams.

The purpose of this study is to help us understand how the communication channels support the software development process and the developers. There are no mandatory questions in our survey and it will likely take 10-15 mins of your time.

The information collected from the survey is to be used for academic purposes only. Please note that it is possible to withdraw your survey submission within 3 weeks, by simply emailing the researchers.

To compensate you for your time you may win a \$10 Amazon gift card if you complete the full questionnaire. We are offering these gift cards to 30% randomly drawn participants who complete the questionnaire.

We would also be happy to share with you the results of the survey, if you are interested.

If you have any questions about this survey, or difficulty in accessing the site or completing the survey, please contact ***** at *****@***** or ***** at *****@*****

Thank you in advance for your participation!

1. What is your gender?

Mark only one oval.

Female

Male

Prefer not to say

Other: _____

2. Where are you from?

3. How old are you?

Mark only one oval.

Under 25

25-35

36-45

46-55

Over 55

4. What is your overall software development experience?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Nur 10 or more

5. What is the name of the GitHub project you are most active in?
Please answer all remaining questions with this project in mind.

6. What is your role in the GitHub project mentioned above?

Mark only one oval.

- I am a maintainer
- I am an active contributor
- I am an occasional contributor
- I use the project resources in my own project(s)
- Other: _____

Release planning

Release planning includes aspects such as which features will be implemented and when they are completed. It also serves as a base to monitor progress within the project.

7. How familiar are you with the release planning process within the project?

Mark only one oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
-
- Not Expert
-

8. What is the primary communication channel(s) used to communicate about release planning?

Check all that apply.

- Face to face
- Email
- Mailing lists
- Telephone
- IRC (Internet Relay Chat)
- Slack
- Gitter
- Google Hangouts
- Skype
- Google groups
- Stack Overflow
- Issue tracking systems
- Pull requests
- Twitter
- Facebook
- Other: _____

9. How well is the number of channel(s) used working for this purpose?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely effective

10. Would you like to justify your rating?

11. What are the reasons behind using this communication channel(s) for this purpose?

Bug fixing

The big fixing process involves discussions about new bugs, prioritisation of bugs, bug assignment, estimation of bug fixing time, etc.

12. How familiar are you with the bug fixing process within the project?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Expert

13. What is the primary communication channel(s) used to communicate about bug fixing?

Check all that apply.

- Face to face
- Email
- Mailing lists
- Telephone
- IRC (Internet Relay Chat)
- Slack
- Gitter
- Google Hangouts
- Skype
- Google groups
- Stack Overflow
- Issue tracking systems
- Pull requests
- Twitter
- Facebook
- Other: _____

14. How well is the number of channel(s) used working for this purpose?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely effective

15. Would you like to justify your rating?

16. What are the reasons behind using this communication channel(s) for this purpose?

Code review

Code review involves developers manually checking the source code of each others to ensure code quality.

17. How familiar are you with the code review process within the project?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Expert

18. What is the primary communication channel(s) used to perform code review?

Check all that apply.

- Face to face
- Email
- Mailing lists
- Telephone
- IRC (Internet Relay Chat)
- Slack
- Gitter
- Google Hangouts
- Skype
- Google groups
- Stack Overflow
- Issue tracking systems
- Pull requests
- Twitter
- Facebook
- Other: _____

19. How well is the number of channel(s) used working for this purpose?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely effective

20. Would you like to justify your rating?

21. What are the reasons behind using this communication channel(s) for this purpose?

User support

The user support process involves communicating with the project's users to assist, troubleshoot, and collect issues reported by the users.

22. How familiar are you with the user support process within the project?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Expert

23. What is the primary communication channel(s) used to communicate with the users?

Check all that apply.

- Face to face
- Email
- Mailing lists
- Telephone
- IRC (Internet Relay Chat)
- Slack
- Gitter
- Google Hangouts
- Skype
- Google groups
- Stack Overflow
- Issue tracking systems
- Pull requests
- Twitter
- Facebook
- Other: _____

24. How well is the number of channel(s) used working for this purpose?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely effective

25. Would you like to justify your rating?

26. What are the reasons behind using this communication channel(s) for this purpose?

Recruiting new developers

Recruiting new developers involves getting new qualified developers to contribute to the source code of a project. A developer could voluntarily contribute or be invited to contribute by the maintainers.

27. How familiar are you with the process of recruiting new developers within the project?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Expert

28. What is the primary communication channel(s) used to identify new potential contributors?

Check all that apply.

- Face to face
- Email
- Mailing lists
- Telephone
- IRC (Internet Relay Chat)
- Slack
- Gitter
- Google Hangouts
- Skype
- Google groups
- Stack Overflow
- Issue tracking systems
- Pull requests
- Twitter
- Facebook
- Other: _____

29. How well is the number of channel(s) used working for this purpose?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely effective

30. Would you like to justify your rating?

31. What are the reasons behind using this communication channel(s) for this purpose?

Project promotion

Promoting the project involves increasing the awareness about the project to attract more users.

32. How familiar are you with the process of promoting the project?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Expert

33. What is the primary communication channel(s) used to promote the project?

Check all that apply.

- Face to face
- Email
- Mailing lists
- Telephone
- IRC (Internet Relay Chat)
- Slack
- Gitter
- Google Hangouts
- Skype
- Google groups
- Stack Overflow
- Issue tracking systems
- Pull requests
- Twitter
- Facebook
- Other: _____

34. How well is the number of channel(s) used working for this purpose?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely effective

35. Would you like to justify your rating?

36. What are the reasons behind using this communication channel(s) for this purpose?

Documentation

Documentation involves all the communications related to improving the documentation docs.

37. How familiar are you with the documentation process within the project?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Expert

38. What is the primary communication channel(s) used to discuss documentation issues?

Check all that apply.

- Face to face
- Email
- Mailing lists
- Telephone
- IRC (Internet Relay Chat)
- Slack
- Gitter
- Google Hangouts
- Skype
- Google groups
- Stack Overflow
- Issue tracking systems
- Pull requests
- Twitter
- Facebook
- Other: _____

39. How well is the number of channel(s) used working for this purpose?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely effective

40. Would you like to justify your rating?

41. What are the reasons behind using this communication channel(s) for this purpose?

Thank you very much!

42. How would you like to be contacted if you are a prize winner?

43. Are you willing to do a quick follow-up interview to help our research? If yes, please leave your e-mail below.

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